

THE OUTLOOK FOR ADVANCED FILAMENTS, FIBERS AND WHISKERS

Key Address

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The principle of combining fibrous materials to reinforce a matrix has existed perhaps since the beginning of time. One of the most common examples of this principle to be found in nature is in bamboo where cellulose fibers are bound together in a matrix of lignin to form a very strong, stiff, lightweight composite. Men have employed this same principle since pre-biblical times when, for example, they combined straw with clay to form bricks.

But outside of a few specific instances, the potentials of this principle remained largely untapped in the intervening centuries, and men depended primarily on monolithic materials to meet their technical needs. It wasn't until the early 20th century that the technical demands of a rapidly expanding industrialized society aroused new interest in fiber reinforced composites. The first pneumatic tire which used cotton yarns to reinforce rubber was a classic example of the use of this principle. The intervening years have seen enormous improvements in tire performance and reliability, aided substantially by the development of manmade fibers for reinforcement - starting with rayon and then nylon, polyester, and now Kevlar® aramid.

Similarly, plastics reinforced with fibers have made great strides as engineering materials since 1909 when cotton was first used to reinforce phenolic resins in high pressure laminates. One of the most significant advances occurred in the early 1940's when low pressure fabrication systems for molding glass reinforced plastics were developed by Owens-Corning working with the U.S. Army Air Force Material Command. The first application was a support panel for self-sealing gasoline tanks in military aircraft. While the growth of the glass reinforced plastic market and the technology supporting it has been phenomenal since this modest beginning, it was not always easy, nor has it just happened by accident.

In 1947, just after World War II, with military usage essentially discontinued, fiber glass sales diminished to less than a half-million pounds per year. Technical problems in both fiber manufacture and composite production were many, and engineers, with their characteristic caution, were reluctant to use these new materials which they did not fully understand and which had little performance history. Technical problems started to yield to intensive research and development by both industry and government, and aggressive development of civilian markets and lower cost products to serve them was undertaken by glass fiber producers and others. By 1953, sales had climbed to about 25 MM lbs, still not spectacular, but clearly the advent of fiber reinforced plastics as versatile engineering materials was here. The rest is history - annual world glass fiber sales for reinforcing grew to nearly 100 MM lbs by 1960, trebled by 1970, and by 1975 are expected to treble again. And "fiber glass" is a household word used for everything from tennis rackets and boats to high performance rocket engine cases.

This history is no doubt familiar to most of you but it is useful to recount in order to set the stage for the introduction of the so called "advanced fibers" which took place during the Sixties. Led by boron, graphite and the newer aramids, these fibers as a class combine high tensile strength and high modulus with low density giving rise to composite structures having exceptionally high ratios of strength and stiffness to weight.

Indeed, the frontiers of specific strength and stiffness had been significantly pushed out - truly opening entirely new technological possibilities. Both private industry and government, dazzled by the engineering potential of these new materials (as well they should be), have lavished massive funds on their development - a conservative guess would be a total of well over a quarter of a billion dollars since their introduction.

Despite this enormous collective effort, success has been spotty at best. While there has been notable technical progress in our understanding of these materials, much of which will be discussed at this Conference, application of this knowledge has not always been as noteworthy. True, we have seen some brilliant successes, particularly in the aerospace field, but we have also witnessed some spectacular failures. Either way, the cost has always been high.

So today, over 10 years after their introduction, usage of these fibers in composite applications still remains relatively small - probably under a half million pounds per year - and most of this is going into either a few specialized aerospace applications or into sporting goods. Moreover, the production of these advanced fibers is still largely unprofitable.

So here is where we are - we have made an important advance in the technology of engineering materials but have yet to learn how to make a commercial success of it. At this point, I believe it is important to reflect on why and what are the chances of overcoming our problems. On the answers depends the future of the whole field of advanced composites. Certainly, the producers of these advanced fibers will eventually lose interest in continued deficits unless they can see a reasonable chance to develop a viable business profitable enough to recover the already expended development costs and make a return for their stockholders, perhaps even in this generation.

While this situation may seem somewhat bleak, it is not unlike the situation which existed in the development of glass fiber reinforced composites after World War II. This being the case, then, I believe the same intensive effort will be required to solve the interrelated economic, technical, and marketing problems for advanced fibers as was done for the glass fibers almost three decades ago.

Let us first consider economics and again, a look at history is useful. When first introduced, glass reinforced plastics (GRP) were not competitive with materials such as metals and wood in terms of specific tensile strength and modulus per dollar, and few foresaw that GRP would replace these materials in many applications. So GRP would have to offer something more than the conventional materials - and they do - primarily high tensile and modulus to weight, excellent resistance to environmental degradation, and good electrical characteristics. It was these properties coupled with ease of fabrication into complex shapes that made GRP competitive on a "value-in-use" basis. As glass price lowered, it became more and more cost-competitive with conventional materials, and now, with a variety of glass fiber products selling at under \$.50/lb, GRP is on the threshold of economic equality as a material of construction with metals and

wood. No wonder the future growth prospects for glass reinforced plastics looks bright. There is one key problem though - the current gross profit margins for glass fiber are not high (estimates range from 8-12%), and since glass fiber production is highly capital intensive, margins will have to improve to attract the necessary capital to keep pace with demand. The opportunity for better margins appears good as wood and metals continue their trend toward higher prices.

The economic problem for advanced fibers is even more critical. To be competitive with E-glass fibers on a dollar per unit of specific modulus, graphite would have to sell at between \$3 and \$4/lb and aramids at \$1-\$2/lb in terms of 1975 dollars. In dollars per unit of tensile strength, the point of equivalency with E glass is even lower. It seems unlikely that either graphite or aramid fibers will reach such low price levels in the foreseeable future even with significant production growth. One of the hopes for lower cost in the case of graphite is the successful commercialization of the pitch-precursor process. This is under active development by Union Carbide in the U.S., and perhaps others. There has been much public speculation that this product ultimately could be sold for less than \$10/lb. - perhaps even under \$5/lb. This remains to be seen, but if it does happen, it will be an important and necessary step to the ultimate growth in usage of graphite to the multimillion pound levels that have been predicted for it.

Some varieties of high modulus aramid fibers are already selling at under \$10/lb but major usage of these fibers in composites has not yet developed even though their specific properties are significantly superior to glass. So even if prices for graphite and aramid do go below \$5/lb, it is apparent that this alone may not generate volume sales. To develop any significant sales, advanced fibers must be used efficiently and innovatively in ways which extend the engineering capabilities of composites beyond the limits now imposed by glass fiber reinforcement. We should remember that this is the same problem that faced glass fibers in the 1940's and their success lay in their ability to do a job better or to do a job that couldn't be done another way. Where the advanced fibers have done this, they have been successful.

And this brings us to the second problem - technology. Certainly the composite manufacturing technology which already exists for glass gives the advanced fibers a tremendous advantage compared with where glass was in the Forties. But there are several areas which require continued intensive technical effort if advanced composites are to realize their potential. First: The consistency of properties of both the fibers and the composites made from them must be improved. If these materials are ever to be used in ways which take full advantage of their properties,

confidence in their reliability must be generated by real progress in product uniformity. Second: More must be learned about the relationship of composite properties to requirements of the applications if parts made from advanced composites are to be designed in the most cost-effective way. These materials will always be too expensive to use them inefficiently. Third: As a corollary, development must also continue on low cost composite manufacturing technology. Fourth: The understanding of the interrelationship of fiber and matrix properties must be expanded. This includes the use of more than one fiber as a reinforcement in the composite where the combination can produce better properties than can be achieved with either fiber used alone. This so-called "hybrid" concept offers the potential of tailoring properties to the need for maximum cost-effectiveness. Fifth: Engineers must continue to approach composites as materials of construction with an open mind - be willing to try something new, and not be confined to the comfortable armchair of the familiar. This does not mean lowering of standards of performance but a willingness to seek a better way to do the job.

These in the broadest sense are some (but certainly not all) of the areas of technology which must be attacked if advanced composites are to come of age. Moreover, these must be digested before anything more than incremental improvements in fiber properties will occur. The major advances in fiber technology will be in the areas of consistency of properties, and the introduction of less costly product forms (e.g. chopped fiber molding compounds) and more easily handled materials (e.g. woven fabrics, chopped strand mat, rovings, and hybrid tapes and fabrics).

Last, the market environment and the problems related to it are important to consider. It is obvious that innovative usage is the keystone of the growth of advanced fibers in composites since no large replacement opportunities exist at current or foreseeable prices. This takes time, money, and imagination. At times, these advanced materials seem to be the solution to a problem that doesn't exist yet. And in the case of graphite and boron, another problem is that a small market has been divided among a number of fiber manufacturers engaged in aggressive competition. Thus, none of them has an opportunity to generate the volume or revenue necessary to make it a paying proposition so far. Therefore, the cash flow curve is still negative and may continue to be so for some time. The net result will probably be a continuation of the consolidation of the market into the hands of fewer but stronger manufacturers. The question is how long even the stronger graphite and boron fiber producers can persist in the face of tight capital supply, cost inflation, world recession, and general economic uncertainty. It is vital that one or two markets of some volume potential at current prices be opened if these problems are not to force